

Gazi Deli Huseyn Pasha Mosque in Rethymno

also known as “Neradje Mosque”, “Nerantze Mosque”, “Gazi Hüseyin Paşa Camii”, “Neratzı Mosque”, “Church of Our Lady”, “Τζαμί Νερατζέ”

By Sofia Kane, University of Crete

Entry tags: Rethymno, Greece, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Greek, Aegean, Islam, Crete, Religious Place, Language, Turkic, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi

This building was first established as the Church of Our Lady in the second half of the sixteenth century, while Crete was under Venetian rule. During this period, the church belonged to the Augustinian monks and had an associated monastery. After the Ottoman conquest of Rethymno in AD 1646, the church was converted into the Gazi Hüseyin Paşa Mosque, named for the commander of the Ottoman army in Crete from 1646-1656. It was later nicknamed Camii Neratze, meaning “Mosque of Bitter Oranges” in Greek. The mosque is a rectangular structure oriented on the east-west axis of the original church, and features three domes added after the conversion to a mosque. A carved entryway that is likely from the Venetian period is located on the northern wall of the mosque, and a türbe (mausoleum) is located to the south of the mosque. Hüseyin Pasha created a vakf to support the mosque that consisted of the revenue from several settlements near Rethymno, Kissamos, Agios Vasileios, and Chania. The complex included an imaret (soup kitchen), library (converted from the chapel of Corpus Christi), and school, in addition to the mosque (converted from the church of the Augustinian monastery). The conversion of the church into a mosque entailed rebuilding the south wall, adding domes to the roof, and adding a new internal support system for the domes. According to Evliya Celebi, an Ottoman traveller who visited Crete between 1668 and 1671, the mosque complex featured a soup kitchen (imaret) that fed both the rich and the poor. The current minaret was built in 1890/1891 by Giorgios Daskalakis, who also built the bell tower of a nearby church. The mosque was restored in the 1980s, and the mosque is currently used as a concert and lecture hall.

Date Range: 1550 CE - 1924 CE

Region: Neratze Mosque

Region tags: Greece

Neratze Mosque in Rethymno, Crete

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Giapitsoglou, Konstantinos. “Gazi Deli Hüseyin Pasha Complex,” in *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*. Edited by Ersi Brouskari. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

– Source 1: Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Translated by Seyit Kahraman. Vol. 8/1. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.

– Source 2: Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi*. Edited by Seyit Ali Kahraman, Yücel Dağlı, and Robert Dankoff. Vol. VIII. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2003.

Notes: Translation is available in Modern Turkish; transliteration is available in Ottoman Turkish.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://historicalcrete.ims.forth.gr/Toponyms/>

– Source 1 Description: Kostas II. Papadakis, "Santa Maria" in HistoricalCrete online map.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is located on the central street through the Old Town of Rethymno.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Individual

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - No

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: Monotheistic God

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Deli Huseyn Pasha (governor)

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: The minaret features an inscription (Ottoman language in Arabic text).

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: One türbe (mausoleum) is associated with the mosque.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Türbe (mausoleum).

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 50-250

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: daily/yearly

Notes: Small-scale rituals (daily prayers) occurred five times daily; large-scale rituals of Eid ul-Adha, Eid ul-Fitr, and additional Ramadan prayers occurred annually.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Goat, sheep, or cow for Eid ul-Adha

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– No

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– No

↳ Private contributions

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Vakf

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

–Yes [specify]: Imaret

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: Annually

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Non-Muslim members of society may or may not have participated in Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr celebrations in Rethymno.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 50-250

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Vakf

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Gazi Deli Huseyn Pasha Mosque in Rethymno, Giapitsoglou, Konstantinos. "gazi Deli Hüseyin Pasha Complex," in *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*. Edited by Ersi Brouskari. Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008. p.436-439

Reference: Gazi Deli Huseyn Pasha Mosque in Rethymno, Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi*. Edited by Seyit Ali Kahraman, Yücel Dağlı, and Robert Dankoff. Vol. VIII. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2003.

Reference: Gazi Deli Huseyn Pasha Mosque in Rethymno, Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi*. Translated by Seyit Kahraman. Vol. 8/1. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.